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“PINOY POLLS”

Stage sets for masked yet eloquent man;
game rolls for innovative yet improbable plan.
With glittering promises in demand,
with pretentious mind, it shall begin.

Change scripts for persuasive yet argumentative stand;
peace speaks for impressive yet unattainable errand.
With modified songs in broadcast,
with promising name, it shall cast.

Actor enters for innocent yet unqualified idea;
athlete stands for noble yet unethical lea.
With cordial handshake in step,
with sweet smile, it shall reap.

Government bribes for glaring yet ordered survey;
voter falls for voluntary yet marked money.
With targeted board in poverty,
with murky chic, it shall be reality.

Hope fades for contented yet oppressed employee;
voice shuns for concealed yet reluctant glee.
With shackled hands in starvation,
with red tummy, it shall return.